

Neighborhood-School Sorting and School Effects on Primary School Outcomes

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Data availability: This study uses non-public microdata from Statistics Netherlands (CBS) and the Netherlands Cohort Study on Education (NCO). Under certain conditions, these data are accessible for statistical and scientific research. For further information, please visit the websites of CBS (www.cbs.nl/en-gb/onze-diensten/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research) and NCO (www.nationaalcohortonderzoek.nl/onderzoek).

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Abstract

Neighborhoods and schools are key extrafamilial contexts shaping children's educational outcomes. Residential and school *selection* are often closely intertwined: some parents move to access desirable schools, or choose schools depending on residential constraints. Yet most research on contextual *effects* treats these processes as a statistical identification problem rather than as a substantive topic of interest. In this study, we develop a new way of thinking about residential choice and school effects. Instead of asking whether neighborhoods and schools have independent effects on student outcomes, we ask whether considering the school supply in residential choice matters for children's education. In other words, does school-motivated residential mobility pay off in terms of children's academic performance? Using geo-coded longitudinal register data from the four largest Dutch cities (Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, and Utrecht), we examine how families sort into neighborhoods-school structures and how this shapes children's formal track recommendations in the transition to secondary school. We find that university-educated families are somewhat more likely to relocate to neighborhoods with higher-reputation schools, net of other neighborhood features. However, we find no evidence that (contextual effects on) educational outcomes depend on whether parents consider the school supply in their residential choices.

1. Introduction

Extensive research shows that the social contexts children are exposed to outside the household, most notably neighborhoods and schools, can shape their educational trajectories, long-term socio-economic outcomes, and broader development and well-being. Children growing up in advantaged contexts tend to benefit from institutional, social, and environmental resources, while exposure to contextual disadvantage can limit life chances (for reviews, see Nieuwenhuis & Hooimeijer, 2016; Sharkey & Faber, 2014; Van Ewijk & Slegers, 2010). Understanding how families sort into contextual (dis)advantage, and how these contexts shape children's outcomes, is therefore central to explaining social inequality and the intergenerational transmission of (dis)advantage.

A key question in this field is how neighborhoods and schools are interconnected. These contexts are linked in several ways. First, residential and school choices are often jointly made: depending on the school allocation system and housing market, some (prospective) parents move to access desirable schools, or choose schools based on their place of residence – either by attending a local school or “opting out” (Agostinelli et al., 2024; Lareau & Goyette, 2014). With the global expansion of school choice (Musset, 2012), these dynamics have become more complex, as residence is no longer a prerequisite for school access. Second, neighborhood and school effects may not operate independently. Schools can be an institutional and social-interactive pathway through which neighborhoods shape educational outcomes (Ainsworth, 2002; Jencks & Mayer, 1990; Sykes & Musterd, 2011), and (dis)advantage in one context may be reinforced or offset by conditions in another (Gaias et al., 2018; Levy, 2022).

Despite theoretical recognition of these links, empirical research on contextual *selection* and *effects* has largely developed in parallel. Studies on neighborhood-school selection mostly focus on segregation patterns, paying less attention to implications for children's educational outcomes. Conversely, research on contextual effects often treats selection as a statistical

identification issue rather than a substantive topic (Schachner & Sampson, 2020). A burgeoning literature has begun to jointly examine neighborhood and school effects (e.g., Brännström, 2008 [Sweden]; Kauppinen, 2008 [Finland]; Kuyvenhoven & Boterman, 2021 [NL]; Nieuwenhuis et al., 2021 [UK]; Owens, 2010 [USA]; Wodtke et al., 2023 [USA]). Yet, as Rich and Owens (2023) argue, the focus often remains on which context matters more, or on isolating the effect of one while controlling for the other. This obscures how contexts constitute each other, limiting insight into the mechanisms behind contextual effects and, from a life course perspective, their social, structural, and historical embeddedness (Levy, 2022; Rich & Owens, 2023).

This study contributes by explicitly integrating contextual selection into the study of contextual effects. We study the extent to which families sort into neighborhoods based on the local school supply, and how this shapes children's educational outcomes in the Netherlands. Noteworthy is that we do not, then, simply ask whether the neighborhood matters for student outcomes, but whether considering the local school supply in residential decisions pays off. Ultimately, from a sociological perspective, we would not only want to know whether contexts matter, but also whether school-related motivations for choosing a neighborhood, or the lack of opportunities for doing so, lead to the expected benefits or disadvantages.

We use geo-coded register data (2004-2020) with detailed information on family background, residential histories, and educational trajectories. The outcome of interest is the formal track recommendation students receive for secondary school. This transition marks the onset of ability tracking, and is therefore key for understanding educational inequality. The Netherlands is an interesting case given its long tradition of free school choice: there are no catchment areas, nearly all schools are publicly funded, and most (urban) families have access to many nearby schools. Although families in principle do not need to move to access (desirable) schools, residential segregation is the main driver of primary school segregation (Boterman, 2019). This raises questions about the extent to which (subgroups of) families use

the housing market for school choice, and with what consequences. We focus on the four largest metropolitan regions (Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, and Utrecht), accounting for about 25% of the national student population. While related research has concentrated on Amsterdam (Boterman, 2021, 2022; Kuyvenhoven & Boterman, 2021), our approach allows for comparisons across regions with different housing markets and demographic profiles.

Methodologically, we extend a two-step approach developed by Ioannides and Zabel (2008) and Van Ham et al. (2018) (for applications, see Borgen & Zachrisson, 2024; Galster et al., 2024; Santiago et al., 2024; Troost et al., 2022). First, we estimate families' likelihood of moving to certain neighborhoods based on standard neighborhood characteristics (housing, demographics, amenities) and features of nearby schools. From these models, we derive a measure capturing the contribution of the local school supply to residential choice. Second, we use this measure in models predicting children's track recommendations to assess whether (contextual effects on) educational outcomes vary depending on whether parents consider the local school supply when deciding where to live.

2. Background

2.1 Toward the Integrated Study of Neighborhood-School Structures

A large literature has examined neighborhood and school effects in education. As noted, much of this work has centered on a single context, overlooking how social contexts shape one another through selection processes, and how school and neighborhood influences on individual outcomes accumulate or intersect. Recently, scholars have increasingly turned to the joint study of these contexts. Several narrative reviews have outlined the theoretical foundations for how neighborhoods and schools together shape children's outcomes (Brazil, 2016; Gaias et al., 2018; Johnson, 2012). Drawing on Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological systems theory, this work views children as embedded in multiple microsystems (neighborhoods, schools) that interact

within mesosystems. Empirical research has likewise moved toward integrated analyses of neighborhood and school effects (e.g., Brännström, 2008; Nieuwenhuis et al., 2021; Wodtke et al., 2023).

Despite this progress, empirical work on contextual effects remains largely disconnected from work on how families sort into contexts of (dis)advantage. Sorting processes are often treated as a statistical nuisance rather than a process worthy of investigation (Schachner & Sampson, 2020). Recognizing this gap, Rich and Owens (2023) call for the study of “neighborhood-school structures,” defined as “local contextual formations that are shaped by policies, institutional practices, demographic forces, and responsive sorting behaviors” (p. 298). This perspective urges scholars to integrate sorting processes into outcome-oriented research.

Following this call, we focus explicitly on the sorting processes that produce the neighborhood-school structures in which children grow up. First, we examine the extent to which Dutch families consider the local school supply in residential decisions, net of other well-known predictors of residential choice. Second, we assess whether associations between contextual characteristics and children’s educational outcomes depend on parents’ ability to do so – i.e., whether school-related residential mobility “pays off.”

2.2 Neighborhood-School Sorting under Free School Choice

Residential and school choices are often closely intertwined. Especially in systems with catchment areas or school districts, “choosing” where to live effectively means choosing a set of schools, creating strong incentives for (prospective) parents to base residential decisions on nearby schools (Agostinelli et al., 2024; Lareau & Goyette, 2014).

These sorting patterns are socially stratified. Affluent families are better positioned to exercise school choice through residential mobility, while lower-income families face greater housing constraints (Cuddy et al., 2020; Holme, 2002; Lareau & Goyette, 2014; Rogne et al.,

2025).¹ Beyond financial resources, families may also differ in how they evaluate options: U.S.-based research suggests that advantaged parents more often consider (proxies of) school quality in residential and school choices, whereas disadvantaged parents prioritize other factors when deciding where to live (such as safety, amenities, or proximity to work), or value aspects of schooling other than test scores or peer composition (Owens, 2017; Rhodes & DeLuca, 2014). Parents' cognitive skills also appear to shape their ability to navigate complex institutional environments, resulting in stratified sorting by school quality (Schachner & Sampson, 2020).

Much of this evidence comes from countries where school access is (or was) tightly linked to residence. School choice has complicated these dynamics. Since the 1980s, most OECD countries have introduced reforms to weaken the residence-school link and equalize educational opportunities (Musset, 2012). These include the introduction of “schools of choice” (e.g., charter, magnet, or private schools), programs to opt out of local schools (e.g., vouchers or bussing programs), and open enrollment or centralized assignment systems (Wilson & Bridge, 2019).

What does this imply for neighborhood-school sorting? On the one hand, school choice introduces socio-spatial strategies that may reduce the role of schools in residential choice. Families may “opt out” of local schools, either because they cannot afford living near desirable schools or because they prioritize non-school factors in residential decisions. Middle-class families settling in diverse, gentrifying neighborhoods while avoiding local schools exemplify the latter (Boterman, 2013). Such strategies are also socially stratified: advantaged families are generally more willing and able to travel further to schools that match their preferences for quality, composition, or other factors (Karsten et al., 2003; Reay & Ball, 1998). On the other

¹ Schools also shape residential patterns *indirectly* by driving up property prices near highly-reputed schools, thereby even affecting households who do not consider school access, including non-parents (Black & Machin, 2011; Nguyen-Hoang & Yinger, 2011).

hand, school choice rarely fully decouples school access from residence. Even under open enrollment, there may be geographically-based admission criteria, as in the UK (Greaves, 2024). Moreover, even without any formal criteria, school choice remains spatially contingent: families often prefer nearby schools for reasons of travel distance, convenience, and community ties (Reay & Ball, 1998). Recent evidence from Sweden’s free choice system shows that strong proximity effects restrict families’ feasible options to very similar schools, limiting their ability to act on other preferences (Mutgan et al., 2025).

In the Netherlands – the case under study – the formal link between residence and school access is weak, limited to geographically-based priority in oversubscribed schools (see Section 2.4). Although families often do not need to move to access schools, proximity is a key factor in school choice (Borghans et al., 2015; Denessen et al., 2005; Karsten et al., 2003), and residential segregation drives much of primary school segregation (Boterman, 2019). Residential mobility before school entry is common (Kuyvenhoven et al., 2022), suggesting these moves partly reflect parental efforts to secure more favorable educational environments.

Only a few Dutch studies have examined how local school supply relates to residential sorting. In Amsterdam, socio-economically advantaged families are more likely to live in or move to advantaged neighborhoods and enroll their children in similarly-composed schools (Boterman, 2021). Furthermore, local school attendance varies by family background and neighborhood composition: advantaged children often attend advantaged schools, even when living in less privileged areas, while disadvantaged children attend schools with disadvantaged peers, also in more affluent areas (Boterman, 2022). Because these studies focus on a single region and do not model residential choice (accounting for other predictors) or its consequences, much remains unknown about how families use the housing market as a strategy for school choice. Accordingly, we ask: *to what extent do different families weigh the local school supply in residential decisions?*

2.3 Consequences of Neighborhood-School Sorting in Education

What are the expected consequences when (prospective) parents incorporate the local school supply into residential decisions for children's educational outcomes? Such sorting may reinforce educational inequalities through *social-interactive*, *institutional*, and *environmental* mechanisms identified in the contextual effects literature (for reviews, see Galster, 2012; Sharkey & Faber, 2014). Children in advantaged neighborhoods and schools are more likely to encounter supportive learning climates, positive role models, high-quality instruction, and safe environments, while exposure to contextual disadvantage can constrain educational prospects.

Evidence from the Netherlands supports the presence of contextual effects. Recent longitudinal research shows that exposure to neighborhood poverty is negatively related to educational attainment, with effects varying by accumulation, duration, timing, and sequencing of exposure (Troost et al., 2023). Other Dutch research using a causal design, exploiting variation in the timing of moves between siblings (cf. Chetty & Hendren, 2018), also finds neighborhood effects, although they appear strongest during secondary school and diminish when outcomes are measured in early adulthood (Beekers, 2024). Cross-sectional studies from the Netherlands further show that neighborhood and school characteristics are associated with educational outcomes when studied separately, but when modeled jointly, neighborhood associations often weaken or disappear while school associations persist (Kuyvenhoven & Boterman, 2021; Sykes & Musterd, 2011). This suggests that schools partly explain neighborhood effects, though research from other countries using formal decomposition finds little evidence that neighborhood influences operate through school quality, composition, or resources (Wodtke et al., 2023).

Importantly, this study does not ask whether exposure to contextual (dis)advantage affects children's outcomes, but whether school-related motivations for choosing a neighborhood actually pay off. From rational-choice and parental-investment perspectives,

families who select neighborhoods with desirable school options arguably aim to improve their children's educational opportunities. However, assessing school quality is difficult: information on school effectiveness is limited, and parents often rely on informal networks or proxies as school composition (Abdulkadiroğlu et al., 2020; Holme, 2002; Lareau, 2014). Recent Swedish research shows that children who move shortly before school entry attend schools with more advantaged student populations, but of similar (value-added) quality to the schools they would have attended had they not moved (Andersson et al., 2025). Furthermore, in systems with free school choice, residential choice is only one of several socio-spatial strategies for accessing desirable educational environments. When moving is unnecessary, unfeasible, undesirable, or guided by other motives, (advantaged) families may still enroll children in desirable schools (Boterman, 2021, 2022). Finally, families who can consider the school supply in residential decisions tend to be socio-economically advantaged, and their children may be less sensitive to contextual (dis)advantage (compensatory advantage model). Together, these factors may distort potential returns to school-related residential mobility.

Against this background, we ask: *does the relation between contextual characteristics and children's educational outcomes depend on parents' ability to consider the local school supply when deciding where to live?*

2.4 Context: Dutch Urban Regions

In the Netherlands, primary school starts at age 4 (compulsory from age 5) and lasts eight years. At the end of primary school (age 12), students are allocated to hierarchically ordered secondary school tracks. Placement is based on a quasi-binding track recommendation that combines teacher assessments and standardized test results.² The system includes practical education

² Teachers recommend one or two adjacent tracks based on students' prior performance and potential other factors, such as motivation and parental involvement. After a standardized exit test, this recommendation may be adjusted

(*praktijkonderwijs*), preparing students with special educational needs for labor market entry, three four-year pre-vocational tracks (*vmbo-b*, *vmbo-k*, *vmbo-gt*), a five-year general track (*havo*), and a six-year pre-university track (*vwo*). Although track mobility is possible, it is limited and socially selective, making initial placement a strong predictor of later attainment (Bles, 2024; Jacob & Tieben, 2009).

The Netherlands has a long tradition of free school choice. Freedom of education has been constitutionally guaranteed since 1917, meaning that all schools – whether public or private – receive state funding. Financial barriers to education are therefore minimal, with over 99% of students attending state-funded schools (OECD, 2017). There are no catchment areas or school districts. During the study period, all regions had open enrollment systems: parents apply directly to their preferred school once their child turns three. Public schools must admit all applicants unless oversubscribed, in which case priority rules apply (e.g., having siblings at the school, attending an affiliated preschool, or living nearby). State-funded private schools may, under certain conditions, select students on religious or ideological grounds. Given the country’s high population density, most families live near many schools (Statistics Netherlands, 2024). In urban regions, popular schools can face capacity constraints, prompting parents to register children as early as possible (sometimes even before the legal age) as some schools maintain unofficial waiting lists. Navigating this process requires implicit knowledge of the system, which tends to favor advantaged families (Lareau, 2015).³

upward (downward adjustments are not permitted). This procedure applies to cohorts in this study. Before school year 2014-2015, the use of a standardized exit test was not mandatory, though most schools administered one. Since 2023-2024, schools must raise recommendations when test results exceed initial teacher recommendations, unless they make a motivated objection.

³ In response to growing concerns about segregation, some municipalities have recently introduced “controlled choice” systems, where families submit preference lists and an algorithm (with priority rules) determines allocation. Such systems were not in place in the period under study but were later introduced in the municipalities of Amsterdam (2014), The Hague (2018), and Utrecht (2021).

This study focuses on the four largest urban regions – Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, and Utrecht – all located in the “Randstad,” an urban conurbation in the west of the country. Compared to rural areas, these regions have higher levels of residential and school segregation (Inspectorate of Education, 2018, 2022), greater residential mobility (Kuyvenhoven et al., 2023), and more school choice opportunities (Statistics Netherlands, 2024; Vogels et al., 2021). At the same time, they differ substantially in socio-demographics and housing and labor markets. Rotterdam’s industrial, port-based economy is reflected in a larger share of residents from lower socio-economic backgrounds, while Amsterdam and Utrecht’s knowledge-based economies attract higher-income, university-educated populations (Troost et al., 2022). The Hague, home to the government and other (inter)national institutions, combines affluent neighborhoods with areas of persistent disadvantage, resulting in pronounced segregation. The spatial distribution of social housing also varies: in Utrecht, social housing is concentrated in suburban areas, while it is more evenly spread in Amsterdam and Rotterdam (Troost et al., 2022). Rising housing prices and pressure on social housing, particularly in Amsterdam and Utrecht, have intensified residential segregation in recent decades (Musterd & Van Gent, 2015). Together, these differences underscore the value of exploring how selection into neighborhood-school structures, and their effects on educational outcomes, vary across regions.

3. Data and Methods

3.1 Data

We use Dutch register data from Statistics Netherlands (CBS), providing detailed information on family background, residential histories, and educational trajectories. All education-related data are integrated in the Netherlands Cohort Study on Education (NCO; for more information, see Haelermans et al., 2020).

Following prior research, we use administrative neighborhoods (*buurten*) as spatial units (Sykes & Musterd, 2011; Troost et al., 2022). Neighborhoods are small, demarcated parts of a municipality that are homogenous in building structure and socio-economic function (e.g., housing, industry, recreation). In our sample, neighborhoods have a median size of 0.5 km² and house about 520 households or 1,190 residents.⁴ Prior Dutch research shows that most residents (~95%) use the same or a similar name as the administrative name to describe their neighborhood, suggesting these areas generally align with perceived neighborhoods, though subjective and formal boundaries may not fully coincide (Permentier et al., 2008).

3.2 Sample Restrictions and Description

This study examines first-time parents whose child entered primary school in 2010 or 2011. These cohorts have the required background information and outcome data, and finished primary school before the Covid-19 pandemic.⁵ We focus on children living in the metropolitan areas of Amsterdam, Utrecht, The Hague, or Rotterdam at school entry, covering about 25% of the national student population. These regions include cities and surrounding municipalities, to include households moving from urban centers to suburban areas, which is common around the

⁴ Neighborhood identifiers are not fully stable over time since boundaries may shift and neighborhoods may merge or split. To ensure consistent treatment of moves across years, and to generate predicted probabilities for all neighborhoods (see Section 3.3.1), we fix the geography to 2006 boundaries. We select 2006 because it has the highest mean address overlap with identifiers in other years across regions. If a neighborhood identifier does not yet exist (before 2006) or no longer exists (after 2006), we identify the neighborhood(s) its addresses map onto in that year and use this to compute (weighted) neighborhood characteristics.

⁵ We need data on family background, residential histories, and neighborhood features from two years before childbirth (~2004 for the 2010 cohort) until students leave primary school (~2019 for the 2011 cohort). Primary school entrants in 2010 are the first cohort in NCO, and income and neighborhood data are available from 2003. Later cohorts could not be included: 2012-2014 cohorts faced Covid-related school closures during or near their final year of primary school, which may affect educational inequalities, and later cohorts lack outcome data.

transition to parenthood (Vidal et al., 2017). The regional boundaries refer to official municipal cooperations in domains like transport, housing, and labor (see Table S.1 and Figure S.1).

We restrict the sample to first-born children (~45%), since residential mobility related to family formation and school choice is most relevant at this stage; younger siblings usually attend the same primary school as their older sibling (also see Andersson et al., 2025; Boterman, 2021). We only include children living with both legal parents or their mother until school entry (~90% of first-born children), excluding those who experienced parental divorce or separation (>9%) or lived in other family constellations (e.g., institutional households, with father, or not with legal parents; <1%). Moves following parental separation are often (also) influenced by other motivations and constraints, complicating inferences about family formation or school-related moves (also see Andersson et al., 2025). This yields samples of 10,793 (Amsterdam), 8,135 (Rotterdam), 7,759 (The Hague), and 5,935 (Utrecht) students ($N_{total} = 32,622$).

For the neighborhood selection model (see Section 3.3), we further restrict the sample to families who moved at least once before the child enters school (age 4). Using mothers' residential histories, we identify the family's last move between two years before childbirth (to capture anticipation effects) and school entry. Note that our sample includes families moving within regions or into these regions from elsewhere, but excludes those moving out (also see Troost et al., 2022).⁶ Overall, 68.4% of families ($N = 22,304$) moved in this period (28.0% before and 40.4% after childbirth), supporting earlier evidence of high childhood mobility in the Netherlands (Bernard & Vidal, 2020; Kuyvenhoven et al., 2022). Moves occurred most

⁶ In the analysis, each region is treated as a local housing market, with all neighborhoods forming a family's choice set (also see Troost et al., 2022; Van Ham et al., 2018). Such choice sets cannot be defined for families leaving the region. While families are not confined to a region and can consider options elsewhere, most search locally due to existing residence, work, and social ties. Of all families living in the regions before moving (including those who moved out), 76.0% stayed within their region. Expanding choice sets beyond regions would complicate their definition and create computational complexities given the >11,000 neighborhoods nationwide.

often just before the transition to parenthood (see Figure S.2). Most moves were short-distance (median = 3.4 km), though distances varied due to inter-regional moves ($SD = 18.1$ km).

Finally, students with missing data (-1.8%) or who moved to neighborhoods with missing data (-0.8%) are excluded. The analytical sample includes 7,211 students in 382 neighborhoods in Amsterdam, 5,307 students in 420 neighborhoods in Rotterdam, 5,199 in 359 neighborhoods in The Hague, and 3,994 in 268 neighborhoods in Utrecht ($N_{total} = 21,711$). Table 1 reports descriptive statistics. Due to our sample restrictions, the sample is relatively advantaged – e.g., 32.6% have university-educated parents (vs. 25.8% in urban regions), mean track recommendations are somewhat higher (4.7 vs. 4.5), and fewer students have a minority background (23.3% vs. 30.9%). This should be kept in mind when interpreting the results.

[Table 1 here]

3.3 Analytical Strategy and Variables

We build on a two-step approach, developed by Ioannides & Zabel (2008) and adapted by Van Ham et al. (2018) (for applications of Van Ham et al. (2018), see Borgen & Zachrisson, 2024; Galster et al., 2024; Santiago et al., 2024; Troost et al., 2022). First, we estimate conditional logit models to assess how families sort into neighborhoods. These models relate neighborhood characteristics (including the local school supply) to residential moves around the transition to parenthood or school entry, and yield predicted probabilities capturing families' likelihood to sort into specific neighborhoods. From these, we construct a “school factor,” quantifying the contribution of the local school supply to residential choice. As detailed below, this is where our approach differs from studies with related methodologies: instead of constructing “correction terms” accounting for selection on all neighborhood characteristics included in the model, we focus on how one specific feature (the local school supply) relates to residential

sorting and educational outcomes. In the second step, we incorporate the school factor into regression models of children’s educational outcomes. This allows us to assess potential advantages for children whose parents consider school quality in residential decisions.

3.3.1 Neighborhood Selection Model

We model neighborhood selection for each region using conditional logit models. Specifically, we estimate the likelihood P_{ij} that family i selects neighborhood j as a function of neighborhood characteristics N_j interacted with family characteristics X_i :

$$P_{ij} = \frac{e^{N_j X_i \beta}}{\sum_{k=1}^J e^{N_k X_i \beta}} \quad (1)$$

The main variable of interest is the *local school supply* – i.e., the average quality or reputation of schools easily accessible to prospective residents. Since families can freely choose schools, many children attend schools just outside their neighborhood. Therefore, this measure is based on all schools located in a neighborhood and its adjacent neighborhoods, defined by shared edges or corners (queen contiguity). School quality is proxied by the share of students receiving a pre-university (*vwo* or *havo/vwo*) track recommendation.^{7,8} Schools with higher shares of pre-university students are not necessarily better schools; they may simply attract more advantaged students. Our goal, however, is not to measure school (value-added)

⁷ Another common proxy for school quality is the mean score on the standardized exit test from Cito. This is not feasible here since schools were not required to administer a standardized test before 2014/2015, and scores from different tests cannot be easily harmonized due to non-random selection of schools into tests. Using test scores rather than track recommendations would therefore introduce substantial missing data and selection issues.

⁸ School quality is measured using data from primary school exit cohorts 2010-2011, as earlier years are unavailable. Some families moved several years earlier, meaning we must assume stability in local school quality over time. School characteristics show moderate to high temporal stability (correlations between 2010 and 2011 values are 0.67-0.95, depending on the indicator). We take the average across two years to reduce noise.

effectiveness but to mirror performance- and composition-based indicators parents typically consult when choosing schools.

The model also includes neighborhood characteristics known to be important in residential choice (Santiago et al., 2024; Troost et al., 2022; Van Ham et al., 2018): (i) *housing characteristics* (i.e., mean dwelling value, share of dwellings built ≥ 2000 , share of social/private housing), (ii) *urbanization degree* and *amenities* (i.e., distance to train station, highway access lane, public green space, and library); and (iii) *demographics* (i.e., share of households with children, and residents with a non-western migration background).⁹ Neighborhood features were taken from the year of the move or the closest available year. Table S.2 provides information on operationalizations and data availability, and Figure S.3 shows correlations. All variables are standardized (mean = 0, $SD = 1$) for the analysis.

All neighborhood characteristics are interacted with family characteristics – i.e., socio-economic status and minority background – to capture heterogeneity in residential choice. Socio-economic status is measured by parental education and household income, which tap into different family resources (financial and cultural). Parental education is defined as the highest degree attained by either legal parent, categorized as: (1) missing, (2) upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED 0-4), (3) bachelor’s or equivalent (ISCED 5-6), and (4) master’s or doctoral degree (ISCED 7-8). Missing values (~8%) are retained to avoid sample selectivity, as education registers are incomplete, especially for vocational and foreign degrees. Household income is measured as the disposable income in the year of the move, expressed in percentiles of the national distribution. Minority background is a binary variable indicating whether at least one parent was born outside Europe (excluding Turkey), the United States,

⁹ Other neighborhood characteristics (e.g., distance to supermarkets or daycare facilities, mean resident income) may also be relevant, but are highly correlated with the covariates already included.

Oceania, Indonesia, or Japan, following Statistics Netherlands' main classification for migration background until 2022.

To derive the “school factor,” we estimate two models: one including all neighborhood-level controls (M_0) and one that adds the local school supply (M_1). The relative change in the predicted probability of choosing the current neighborhood – i.e., $(p_1 - p_0)/p_0$ – quantifies the school factor. It reflects the extent to which the local school supply increases or decreases the likelihood of sorting into the current neighborhood, conditional on other neighborhood features.

Here, our approach deviates from Ioannides & Zabel (2008) and Van Ham et al. (2018), who use neighborhood selection models to construct “correction components” – similar to inverse Mills ratios – to adjust neighborhood effect estimates for residential selection. They also first compute predicted probabilities of moving to each neighborhood. Because these probabilities are collinear and households sort into types of neighborhoods rather than specific areas, they use principal components analysis to reduce them to a smaller set of correction components. These components are included in outcome models as statistical controls. While this approach makes contextual selection explicit in the first step, the correction components aggregate selection across all covariates, obscuring the role of specific neighborhood features. Our approach allows to focus on how one particular feature (the local school supply) relates to residential sorting and educational outcomes.

3.3.2 Contextual Effects Model

In the second step, we estimate contextual effects on children’s educational outcomes, focusing on the formal track recommendations students receive for secondary school at age 11-12. Students may be recommended for (combinations of) six tracks: *pro*, *pro/vmbo-b*, *vmbo-b*, *vmbo-b/k*, *vmbo-k*, *vmbo-k/(g)t*, *vmbo-(g)t*, *vmbo-(g)t/havo*, *havo*, *havo/vwo*, *vwo* (see Section 2.4). Following prior research (Geven, 2024; Timmermans et al., 2018), we treat this as a

continuous measure from 1 (*pro*) to 6 (*vwo*), where 0.5 represents a “half-track” difference (e.g., *vmbo-b/k* vs. *vmbo-b*) and 1 a “full-track” difference (e.g., *vmbo-k* vs. *vmbo-b*). We also construct a binary indicator for receiving a pre-academic track recommendation (*vwo* or *havo/vwo*), which marks the threshold for university preparation.

We first estimate a multilevel model of the form:

$$y_{ij} = \beta + S_{ij}\beta + X_{ij}\beta + u_i + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where y_{ij} denotes the track recommendation for student i in school j , S_{ij} the “school factor” derived from the selection models, and X_{ij} a vector of control variables. These include family characteristics (parental education, mean household income over the primary school years, and minority background) and an index of neighborhood socio-economic status. This measure is constructed using data on the share of residents with (i) low incomes (bottom 40%), (ii) high incomes (top 20%), (iii) social assistance benefits, (iv) unemployment benefits (among residents aged 15-65), and (v) the mean income among income recipients. These indicators are averaged from the child’s birth year (or the year of the move) until the end of primary school, and combined using principal component analysis (one-factor solution explaining 79.2% of the variance) (cf. Borgen & Zachrisson, 2024; Kuyvenhoven et al., 2023).¹⁰ This baseline model tests whether explicitly considering the local school supply in residential choice benefits children’s educational outcomes in itself.

We then add school quality Z_j and its interaction with the school factor to this model:

$$y_{ij} = \beta + S_{ij}\beta + Z_j\beta + (S_{ij}Z_j)\beta + X_{ij}\beta + u_i + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3)$$

¹⁰ Although this variable is measured at the neighborhood level, we do not estimate cross-classified models with students nested in neighborhoods and schools as the number of observations per neighborhood-school combination can be small. Clustering at the school level is more relevant given our main variable of interest and empirically justified by higher intraclass correlations in intercept-only models at the school than at the neighborhood level. Results are very similar when excluding this control, though associations between school quality and track recommendations are somewhat larger, suggesting that neighborhood SES captures part of the contextual effect otherwise attributed to schools.

This allows us to assess whether the effect of the school factor depends on the quality/reputation of the school a child actually attends. Since we do not explicitly model school choice, including school characteristics is essential. Any advantages of choosing a neighborhood based on the local school supply may only accrue to students who ultimately enroll in high-quality schools and may not extend to students attending less advantaged schools, despite living in areas with above-average local options. School quality is measured in “absolute” terms (i.e., the share of pre-university students at the attended school) and in “relative” terms (i.e., its deviation from the mean share of pre-university students in all local schools).

Similar models are estimated for the pseudo-interval measure of track recommendation, and the binary measure of receiving a pre-academic track recommendation. For the latter, we use linear probability models. Models are estimated on the pooled sample (with regional-fixed effects) and by region.

4. Results

4.1 Sorting into Neighborhood-School Structures

Figure 1 summarizes the conditional logit estimates relating the local school supply to residential choice (for exact coefficients, see Table S.3). The baseline model includes the local school supply (i.e., the mean share of pre-university students in nearby schools) and its interactions with family characteristics (parental socio-economic status and minority background). Subsequent models add blocks of control variables capturing (i) housing characteristics, (ii) urbanization degree and amenities, and (iii) demographics, with the last model including all controls. Estimates are presented in log odds: positive values indicate attributes that increase the likelihood of choosing a neighborhood relative to other alternatives, while negative values indicate attributes that decrease this likelihood.

[Figure 1 here]

The base model (blue markers) reveals gross residential sorting by school supply. In all regions, the interaction between household income and the local school supply is positive and statistically significant: a one *SD* increase in household income raises the odds of relocating to a neighborhood with higher-quality or more reputable nearby schools, relative to other alternatives, by $([e^{0.11} - 1] * 100 \approx)$ 11.6% in Amsterdam, 19.7% in Rotterdam, 23.4% in The Hague, and 10.5% in Utrecht. We also observe heterogeneity by parental education. In Amsterdam, higher local school quality reduces the odds of choosing a neighborhood by $([e^{-0.07-0.23} - 1] * 100 \approx)$ 25.9% for parents with vocational degrees, but increases it by $([e^{-0.07+0.38} - 1] * 100 \approx)$ 36.3% for university-educated parents. Similar positive (negative) estimates for university-educated (vocational) parents appear in Rotterdam and The Hague. In Utrecht, the net effect of the local school supply is negative or effectively zero for all education groups, including university-educated parents (-1%). Note that the main effect of the local school supply refers to families with missing parental education (typically those with vocational or foreign degrees) and is negative in all regions except Rotterdam. Finally, among ethnic minority families, higher local school quality is associated with a lower odds of relocating to a given neighborhood (Amsterdam: -22.9%; Rotterdam: -17.3%; The Hague: -58.1%; Utrecht: -42.3%). These associations are controlled for socio-economic status, suggesting that observed sorting by minority background is not explained by income or education differences.

Taken together, baseline results suggest that higher-income, university-educated, non-minority families are more likely to move to neighborhoods with higher-quality or more reputable schools. However, these models do not account yet for other neighborhood characteristics that may drive such patterns. The other models in Figure 1 display results once we do control for other neighborhood characteristics. As expected, estimated residential sorting based on the local school quality attenuates as controls are added. Incorporating housing

characteristics (red markers) reduces income-related heterogeneity in all regions, suggesting that differential access to housing in desirable neighborhoods (partly) explains gross sorting by school supply. Furthermore, adding demographic controls accounts for (much of) the negative interaction between minority background and the local school supply.

Results for the control variables confirm earlier Dutch research on residential choice (Troost et al., 2022; Van Ham et al., 2018). For instance, neighborhood price levels are negatively associated with the likelihood of selecting a neighborhood among less affluent, vocationally-educated families, but these associations are weaker or even positive among socio-economically advantaged families. Neighborhoods with a high share of new construction attract more movers. University-educated parents are more likely to move to, or remain in, more urbanized areas. (Prospective) parents tend to move to neighborhoods with high shares of households with children. Families with a minority background are more likely to select neighborhoods with a high share of minority residents. Full results can be found in Figure S.4.

After adjusting for all neighborhood controls (purple markers), advantaged families remain slightly more likely to select neighborhoods with higher reputation schools, though estimated effects are small and, in some cases, lose statistical significance. Specifically, the positive interaction between household income and the local school supply weakens in Amsterdam ($b = 0.04, p < .05$ vs. $b = 0.11, p < .001$ in base model) and The Hague ($b = 0.08, p < .001$ vs. $b = 0.21, p < .001$), and becomes net zero and insignificant in Utrecht and Rotterdam. The negative interaction between minority background and the local school supply persists only in Utrecht ($b = -0.13, p < .05$ vs. $b = -0.36, p < .001$). The positive association for university-educated families between the local school supply and neighborhood choice remains evident

(e.g., Amsterdam: $b = 0.24, p < .001$ vs. $b = 0.38, p < .001$) or even becomes slightly more pronounced (e.g., Rotterdam: $b = 0.26, p < .001$ vs. $b = 0.10, p > .05$).¹¹

4.2 Contextual Effects in Primary Education

Table 2 shows results from the multilevel regression models predicting students' track recommendations, using the (a) pseudo-interval and (b) binary outcome measure. We report the pooled estimates; region-specific results are available in the supplementary materials (Tables S.4-S.5).

[Table 2 here]

Model 1 shows that the school factor is not associated with students' track recommendations. Estimated effects are essentially zero and statistically insignificant for both outcomes (Model 1a: $b = 0.01, p > .05$; Model 1b: $b = 0.00, p > .05$). In other words, explicitly considering the local school supply in residential decisions does not, in itself, improve children's educational outcomes. Estimates for family characteristics align with prior research: students from higher-income and university-educated families tend to receive higher track recommendations. For example, the predicted probability of receiving a pre-university recommendation is circa 35 percentage points higher for students with university-educated parents than for students whose parents have vocational qualifications (see Model 1b).

¹¹ To assess the sensitivity of the results to our operationalization of the local school supply, we re-estimate the main models using two alternative composition-based proxies: (i) the mean share of university-educated parents and (ii) the median household income in nearby schools. Results are very similar when using parental education but less consistent (particularly in Amsterdam) when using median household income (see Figure S.5). A plausible explanation is that income is a more equivocal proxy for school reputation as it is more sensitive to gentrification.

Controlled for socio-economic status, students with a minority background receive, on average, similar track recommendations as their majority peers (see Models 1a-1b: $b = -0.01, p > .05$).

Models 2 and 3 add measures of the quality of the attended school to test whether any potential benefits of school-related residential mobility are concentrated among students who ultimately enroll in high-quality schools. The results suggest this is not the case. The coefficients for the school factor and its interaction with school quality remain close to zero and statistically insignificant. Both neighborhood socioeconomic status (Model 2a: $b = 0.07, p < .001$) and school quality (Model 2a: $b = 0.10, p < .001$) are, however, positively associated with students' track recommendations. Net of family socioeconomic status and minority background, students in more advantaged neighborhood and school environments tend to receive slightly higher track recommendations. Similar positive associations are found for the binary outcome (neighborhood SES: $b = 0.02, p < .001$; school quality: $b = 0.03, p < .001$). Given the scale of the pseudo-interval outcome ($SD = 1.3$; see Table 1), effects are modest in size. These estimates also likely constitute upper bounds, as contextual selection cannot be fully accounted for.

To summarize, Figure 2 displays average marginal effects of the school factor (Panel a) and school quality (Panel b) at representative values of the other variable. If anything, panel (a) suggests that a higher propensity to choose a neighborhood based on its school supply is associated with slightly higher track recommendations among students attending *less* advantaged schools. Viewed differently, Panel (b) shows that the marginal effect of school quality is somewhat larger for students whose parents were *less* likely to sort into a neighborhood based on its school supply. However, this interaction is insignificant, so should not be overinterpreted. Overall, we find no evidence that contextual effects in education depend on whether parents (can) consider the local school supply in their residential decisions.¹²

¹² The analyses above assume stability in children's residential and school contexts during primary education, though this is not always the case. Children may move to a different neighborhood and, consequently or for other

[Figure 2 here]

5. Conclusion and Discussion

This study sought to connect two strands of research that have largely developed in parallel: research on how families sort into neighborhoods and schools, and research on how these contexts shape children’s education. Prior research suggests that (prospective) parents, especially those from advantaged backgrounds, consider characteristics of nearby schools when deciding where to live before their child enters school. Yet it remained unclear (i) whether such patterns hold in contexts with free school choice, where residence does not formally determine school access; and (ii) whether school-related residential mobility actually translates into better educational outcomes. Responding to Rich and Owens’ (2023) call to study “neighborhood-school structures,” we examined whether families consider the local school supply in residential decisions and, crucially, whether doing so yields educational returns in terms of children’s formal track recommendations for secondary school. We addressed these questions using geo-coded register data from the four largest Dutch urban regions (2004-2020).

We argued that contextual sorting, and particularly the importance young families may attach to local schools in residential decisions, must be explicitly linked to children’s outcomes. Only by doing so can we assess whether school-related residential mobility pays off. Classical neighborhood-effects research estimates the impact of contextual (dis)advantage after families have settled, even though these exposures may reflect selection processes only loosely related to parents’ original motivations. Families may, for instance, move for housing quality or safety,

reasons, change schools during this period. This is quite common in our sample (which is partly selected on residential mobility): 29.5% of students move to another neighborhood after starting primary school, and 53.1% of these movers also change schools ($N = 3,361$). Another group of students switches schools without moving neighborhoods ($N = 2,604$). Re-estimating the main models while excluding all students who change schools yields highly similar results (see Table S.6), indicating that school mobility does not distort the findings.

with educational advantages emerging as by-products of such sorting. Our approach directly models the role of the local school supply in residential decisions and then asks whether this translates into educational benefits, net of other contextual influences.

Our findings show that parents with higher incomes, university degrees, and non-minority backgrounds are more likely to move to neighborhoods with higher-quality or more reputable schools. Once standard determinants of residential choice (housing characteristics, amenities, and socio-demographics) are taken into account, most of these associations weaken or disappear. For instance, income differences largely fade, suggesting that much of the gross income sorting reflects unequal access to desirable housing rather than stratified neighborhood-school preferences. However, school quality remains more salient in the residential decisions of university-educated families in most regions. More broadly, the modest effect sizes suggest that, in a national context characterized with free school choice, other socio-spatial strategies (such as opting out of local schools) may be more important than residential mobility (also see Boterman, 2021).

Turning to the educational outcomes, we find no evidence that school-motivated residential mobility is related to children's educational outcomes. Consistent with previous research, attending an advantaged school and living in a socio-economically advantaged neighborhood are positively associated with children's formal track recommendations (Beekers, 2024; Kuyvenhoven & Boterman, 2021; Sykes & Musterd, 2011). However, children whose parents considered the local school supply when choosing where to live do not receive higher track recommendations than comparable peers, nor do they benefit more from attending higher-quality schools. Possible explanations are that parents rely on imperfect indicators of school quality, that free school choice allows families to access schools without moving, and that families able to consider the school supply are already relatively advantaged, limiting the potential gains from such moves.

More broadly, our study invites a reconsideration of how contextual effects research conceptualizes selection. Rather than treating selection as noise to be filtered out, future work may ask whether, when, and for whom contextual sorting yields (dis)advantages. Such an approach raises important questions beyond education: Do residential moves aimed at improving economic opportunities lead to better labor market outcomes? Do firms relocating to optimize transport links actually reduce travel time? Integrating sorting and outcomes can clarify our understanding of how contexts matter.

Several limitations warrant mention. First, we do not explicitly model school choice. Ideally, one would model how the local school supply shapes residential decisions *and* how families select schools conditional on where they live. To the best of our knowledge, current statistical frameworks do not support such joint modeling. Relatedly, residential sorting not only responds to but also helps produce local school landscapes: neighborhood characteristics are linked to school reputations and changes in the school supply, such as openings or closures (Burdick-Will et al., 2013), which can create feedback loops our design cannot capture.

Despite these limitations, our study offers a clear conclusion: school-related residential mobility is slightly socially stratified, yet do not meaningfully shape children's educational outcomes. This challenges widely held assumptions about the importance and benefits of residential mobility and underscores the need to more closely align choice processes with the outcomes families hope to secure.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1. Student and neighborhood descriptives.

	All	Amsterdam	Rotterdam	The Hague	Utrecht
Gender (female = 1)	49.3%	49.5%	49.8%	49.1%	48.9%
Minority background (yes = 1)	23.3%	25%	25.6%	23.8%	16.3%
Education level					
missing	8.1%	7.5%	8.8%	9.7%	6.0%
ISCED 0-4	33.2%	32.0%	40.4%	34.8%	23.9%
ISCED 5-6	26.1%	25.7%	26.9%	26.2%	25.5%
ISCED 7-8	32.6%	34.7%	24.0%	29.4%	44.6%
Household income (year move)	67.9 (23.1)	68.3 (23.7)	64.8 (22.9)	66.8 (23.5)	72.8 (21)
Track recommendation [1-6]	4.7 (1.2)	4.8 (1.2)	4.6 (1.3)	4.7 (1.2)	4.9 (1.2)
pre-vocational I	17.9%	16.4%	21.7%	19.8%	13.3%
pre-vocational II	23.0%	21.8%	25.0%	24.2%	20.8%
senior general	30.3%	31.4%	28.8%	30.6%	29.9%
pre-university	28.8%	30.4%	24.5%	25.4%	36.0%
<i>N_{students}</i>	21,711	7,211	5,307	5,199	3,994
Mean house value ($\times 1000\text{€}$)	241.4 (130.0)	255.0 (104.0)	199.7 (93.9)	245.4 (164.2)	282.4 (142.0)
Share social housing (%)	29.0 (25.8)	26.9 (22.5)	32.8 (27.3)	29.5 (27.5)	25.0 (24.4)
Share private housing (%)	14.7 (13.0)	17.2 (13.8)	11.6 (11.8)	15.1 (12.7)	15.1 (12.8)
Share houses ≥ 2000 (%)	12.9 (23.4)	11.0 (19.6)	13.8 (24.4)	13.5 (24.9)	13.2 (24.6)
Distance highway (km)	1.7 (1.0)	1.6 (0.8)	1.9 (1.0)	1.7 (1.2)	1.7 (1.0)
Distance train (km)	4.9 (4.2)	4.5 (3.3)	6.5 (5.8)	3.5 (2.2)	4.5 (3.4)
Distance public green (km)	0.6 (0.6)	0.7 (0.7)	0.5 (0.4)	0.6 (0.5)	0.6 (0.5)
Distance library (km)	1.7 (1.2)	1.9 (1.3)	1.7 (1.3)	1.3 (0.8)	1.9 (1.4)
Share households with children (%)	35.3 (13.3)	36.1 (12.4)	36.2 (12.3)	33.9 (14.9)	34.5 (13.7)
Share minority background (%)	13.5 (15.1)	12.7 (14.2)	15.2 (15.9)	14.8 (17.0)	10.0 (11.2)
Mean share pre-uni. students (%)	27.4 (11.7)	28.6 (10.8)	21.7 (9.3)	28.9 (12.9)	32.6 (10.9)
<i>N_{neighborhood-years}</i>	13,408	3,344	4,216	3,464	2,384

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: Cells report percentages for categorical variables, and means (with standard deviations in brackets) for continuous variables. See Section 3.3 for the operationalization of all variables.

Figure 1. Results conditional logit models, role of local school supply in residential choice.

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: N = 21,711 (Amsterdam: 7,211; Rotterdam: 5,307; The Hague: 5,199; Utrecht: 3,994). For exact coefficients, see Table S.3. Reference level of parental education = missing. Household income is z-standardized. The model controls for housing characteristics (mean dwelling value, share of dwellings built ≥ 2000 , share of social/private housing); urbanization degree and amenities (distance to train station, highway access lane, public green space, and library); and demographics (share of households with children, and residents with a minority background) (see Section 3.3.1). The whiskers indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Table 2. Results multilevel regression models of a student's track recommendation on school factor, school quality and family characteristics.

	DV: Track recommendation [1-6]			DV: Pre-university track rec. [0/1]		
	(1a)	(2a)	(3a)	(1b)	(2b)	(3b)
Minority background (<i>ref. = no</i>)	0.03 (0.02)	0.04 (0.02)	0.03 (0.02)	0.00 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)
Parental education (<i>ref. = missing</i>)						
ISCED 0-4	-0.12*** (0.03)	-0.11*** (0.03)	-0.12*** (0.03)	-0.02 (0.01)	-0.02 (0.01)	-0.02 (0.01)
ISCED 5-6	0.42*** (0.03)	0.42*** (0.03)	0.42*** (0.03)	0.13*** (0.01)	0.12*** (0.01)	0.13*** (0.01)
ISCED 7-8	0.78*** (0.03)	0.76*** (0.03)	0.77*** (0.03)	0.31*** (0.01)	0.31*** (0.01)	0.31*** (0.01)
Household income	0.20*** (0.01)	0.20*** (0.01)	0.20*** (0.01)	0.06*** (0.00)	0.06*** (0.00)	0.06*** (0.00)
Neighborhood SES	0.10*** (0.01)	0.07*** (0.01)	0.10*** (0.01)	0.03*** (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.00)
School factor	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
School quality (absolute)		0.10*** (0.01)			0.03*** (0.00)	
School factor × school quality (abs)		-0.01 (0.01)			0.00 (0.00)	
School quality (relative)			0.05*** (0.01)			0.02*** (0.00)
School factor × school quality (rel)			-0.01 (0.01)			0.00 (0.00)
Regional fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	4.44*** (0.03)	4.44*** (0.03)	4.45*** (0.03)	0.31*** (0.01)	0.31*** (0.01)	0.31*** (0.01)
var(school)	0.04*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)
var(residual)	1.16*** (0.01)	1.16*** (0.01)	1.16*** (0.01)	0.20*** (0.00)	0.20*** (0.00)	0.20*** (0.00)
Loglikelihood	-32331.54	-32288.25	-32313.87	-13439.01	-13404.71	-13427.64

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N = 21,474$. All continuous predictors are z-standardized. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Figure 2. Average marginal effects of school factor and school quality on a student's track recommendation.

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N = 21,474$. All continuous predictors are z-standardized. Shaded areas denote 95% confidence intervals. Histograms display the distribution of the variable on the x-axis.

Supplementary Materials

Table S.1. Regional definitions.

City	Region	Included municipalities
Amsterdam	Stadsregio	Amsterdam, Aalsmeer, Amstelveen, Beemster, Diemen, Edam-Volendam,
	Amsterdam (2006-2016)	Haarlemmermeer, Landsmeer, Oostzaan, Ouder-Amstel, Purmerend, Uithoorn, Waterland, Wormerland, Weesp, Zaanstad
Rotterdam	Stadsregio	Rotterdam, Albrandswaard, Barendrecht, Bernisse, Brielle, Capelle aan de IJssel,
	Rotterdam (1995-2015)	Hellevoetsluis, Krimpen aan den IJssel, Lansingerland (until 2007: Bergschenhoek, Bleiswijk, Berkel en Rodenrijs), Maassluis, Schiedam, Spijkenisse, Vlaardingen, Westvoorne
The Hague	Stadsgewest	Den Haag, Delft, Leidschendam-Voorburg, Midden-Delfland, Pijnacker-
	Haaglanden (1992-2015)	Nootdorp, Rijswijk, Wassenaar, Westland, Zoetermeer
Utrecht	Bestuur Regio	Utrecht, Bunnik, De Bilt, Houten, IJsselstein, Nieuwegein, Stichtse Vecht (until
	Utrecht (1995-2017)	2011: Maarssen, Breukelen, Loenen), Vianen, Zeist

Figure S.1. Included regions and municipalities.

Note: Amsterdam is *Stadsregio Amsterdam*, Utrecht is *Bestuur Regio Utrecht*, Rotterdam is *Stadsregio Rotterdam* and The Hague is *Stadsgewest Haaglanden* (see Table S.1). The shaded area indicate the city, all other areas the surrounding municipalities.

Figure S.2. Timing of families' latest moves between two years before childbirth and primary school entry.

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N_{families} = 22,304$ (across all four urban regions).

Table S.2. Operationalization of control variables in neighborhood selection model.

Indicator	Period	Definition
Housing		
Average dwelling value	2004-2012	Average dwelling value (<i>WOZ-waarde</i>) of residential objects used as main residences or with home practice; reported for spatial units with ≥ 5 dwellings and ≥ 50 WOZ objects.
Share of dwellings built ≥ 2000	2009-2012	Dwellings recorded in housing register in or after 2000, expressed as share of all dwellings; reported for spatial units with ≥ 20 dwellings.
Share of social housing	2009-2012	Dwellings owned by housing associations or municipal housing companies, expressed as share of all dwellings; reported for spatial units with ≥ 20 dwellings and $\leq 50\%$ unknown ownership.
Share of private rental	2009-2012	Dwellings not owned by housing associations, expressed as share of all dwellings; reported for spatial units with ≥ 20 dwellings and $\leq 50\%$ unknown ownership.
Amenities/accessibility		
Urbanization degree	2003-2012	(1) not urban (< 500 addresses per km^2); (2) hardly urban (500-1000 addresses per km^2); (3) moderately urban (1000-1500 addresses per km^2); (4) strongly urban (1500-2500 addresses per km^2); (5) very strongly urban (> 2500 addresses per km^2).
Distance to train station	2007-2012	Average road distance (in km) of all residents to nearest train station, highway access lane, library, and public green space (i.e., park, green space, recreational area, nature, or forest of at least 1 ha).
Distance to highway access	2006-2012	
Distance to library	2006-2009	
Distance to public green	2006, 2008, 2010, 2012	
Demographics		
Share of residents with non-western migration background	2003-2012	Residents with a migration background classified as non-western (Turkey, Africa, Latin America, and Asia, except Indonesia and Japan), expressed as share of all residents; reported for spatial units with ≥ 50 residents.
Share of households with children	2003-2012	Multi-person households with children (married couples, unmarried couples, and single-parent households), expressed as share of all private households; reported for spatial units with ≥ 10 households.

Source: Key figures for districts and neighborhoods (*Kerncijfers wijken en buurten*), CBS.

Figure S.3. Correlations between variables in neighborhood selection model.

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N_{neighborhood-years}$ = 3,344 (Amsterdam), 4,216 (Rotterdam), 3,464 (The Hague), 2,384 (Utrecht). Non-significant correlations ($p > .05$) are not displayed.

Table S.3. Results conditional logit models, role of local school supply in residential choice.

	base model	housing	amenities	demographics	all controls
Amsterdam ($N_{students} = 7,211, N_{obs} = 2,754,602$)					
Local school supply	-0.07 (0.04)	0.01 (0.05)	-0.10* (0.05)	-0.02 (0.05)	-0.03 (0.05)
HH income \times Local school supply	0.11*** (0.01)	0.04** (0.02)	0.11*** (0.01)	0.12*** (0.01)	0.04* (0.02)
ISCED 0-4 \times Local school supply	-0.23*** (0.05)	-0.13* (0.06)	-0.21*** (0.05)	-0.14* (0.05)	-0.06 (0.06)
ISCED 5-6 \times Local school supply	0.05 (0.05)	0.06 (0.06)	0.06 (0.05)	0.12* (0.05)	0.13* (0.06)
ISCED 7-8 \times Local school supply	0.38*** (0.05)	0.20*** (0.06)	0.34*** (0.05)	0.40*** (0.05)	0.24*** (0.06)
Minority \times Local school supply	-0.19*** (0.03)	-0.18*** (0.04)	-0.20*** (0.03)	0.07* (0.03)	-0.01 (0.04)
Rotterdam ($N_{students} = 5,307, N_{obs} = 2,228,940$)					
Local school supply	0.21*** (0.04)	0.20*** (0.05)	0.19*** (0.05)	0.19*** (0.05)	0.17** (0.05)
HH income \times local school supply	0.18*** (0.02)	0.04* (0.02)	0.16*** (0.02)	0.11*** (0.02)	0.02 (0.02)
ISCED 0-4 \times local school supply	-0.22*** (0.05)	-0.07 (0.06)	-0.17** (0.05)	-0.10 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.06)
ISCED 5-6 \times local school supply	0.04 (0.05)	0.07 (0.06)	0.06 (0.06)	0.11* (0.06)	0.10 (0.06)
ISCED 7-8 \times local school supply	0.10 (0.05)	0.16** (0.06)	0.19*** (0.06)	0.28*** (0.06)	0.26*** (0.06)
Minority \times local school supply	-0.40*** (0.03)	-0.18*** (0.04)	-0.32*** (0.04)	-0.06 (0.04)	-0.06 (0.04)
The Hague ($N_{students} = 5,199, N_{obs} = 1,866,441$)					
Local school supply	-0.22*** (0.05)	-0.23*** (0.06)	-0.28*** (0.06)	-0.29*** (0.06)	-0.22** (0.07)
HH income \times local school supply	0.21*** (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	0.17*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.03)
ISCED 0-4 \times local school supply	-0.21*** (0.06)	-0.07 (0.07)	-0.12 (0.07)	-0.06 (0.07)	0.00 (0.08)
ISCED 5-6 \times local school supply	-0.02 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.07)	0.03 (0.06)	-0.01 (0.07)	-0.03 (0.08)
ISCED 7-8 \times local school supply	0.30*** (0.06)	0.33*** (0.07)	0.41*** (0.06)	0.40*** (0.07)	0.34*** (0.08)
Minority \times local school supply	-0.65*** (0.04)	-0.37*** (0.05)	-0.44*** (0.05)	-0.11* (0.05)	-0.05 (0.06)
Utrecht ($N_{students} = 3,994, N_{obs} = 1,070,392$)					
Local school supply	-0.19** (0.06)	-0.15* (0.07)	-0.18** (0.07)	-0.18* (0.08)	-0.20* (0.08)
HH income \times local school supply	0.10*** (0.02)	0.03 (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.06** (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)
ISCED 0-4 \times local school supply	-0.12 (0.07)	-0.10 (0.08)	-0.15* (0.08)	-0.02 (0.09)	-0.02 (0.09)
ISCED 5-6 \times local school supply	-0.02 (0.07)	-0.01 (0.08)	-0.05 (0.07)	0.03 (0.08)	0.03 (0.09)
ISCED 7-8 \times local school supply	0.18** (0.07)	0.22** (0.07)	0.15* (0.07)	0.23** (0.08)	0.18* (0.08)
Minority \times local school supply	-0.36*** (0.04)	-0.32*** (0.05)	-0.40*** (0.05)	-0.15** (0.05)	-0.13* (0.06)

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Figure S.4. Results neighborhood selection models for control variables.

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N = 21,711$ (Amsterdam: 7,211; Rotterdam: 5,307; The Hague: 5,199; Utrecht: 3,994). The whiskers indicate 95% confidence intervals. Figure shows results from a model where all variables are included simultaneously.

Figure S.5. Results neighborhood selection models using alternative proxies for school quality or reputation.

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N = 21,711$ (Amsterdam: 7,211; Rotterdam: 5,307; The Hague: 5,199; Utrecht: 3,994). Reference level of parental education = missing. Household income is z-standardized. The model with controls includes housing characteristics (mean dwelling value, share of dwellings built ≥ 2000 , share of social/private housing); urbanization degree and amenities (distance to train station, highway access lane, public green space, and library); and demographics (share of households with children, and residents with a minority background) (see Section 3.3.1). The whiskers indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Table S.4. Results multilevel regression models of track recommendation [1-6] on school factor, school quality and family characteristics, by region.

	Amsterdam (N = 7,113)			Rotterdam (N = 5,278)			The Hague (N = 5,185)			Utrecht (N = 3,898)		
	(1a)	(2a)	(3a)	(1a)	(2a)	(3a)	(1a)	(2a)	(3a)	(1a)	(2a)	(3a)
Minority background (ref. = no)	0.04 (0.03)	0.05 (0.03)	0.05 (0.03)	0.04 (0.04)	0.05 (0.04)	0.05 (0.04)	0.06 (0.04)	0.08 (0.04)	0.07 (0.04)	-0.10* (0.05)	-0.09 (0.05)	-0.09 (0.05)
ISCED 0-4	-0.13* (0.05)	-0.13* (0.05)	-0.13* (0.05)	-0.05 (0.06)	-0.05 (0.06)	-0.05 (0.06)	-0.16** (0.06)	-0.15** (0.06)	-0.16** (0.06)	-0.15* (0.07)	-0.15* (0.07)	-0.15* (0.07)
ISCED 5-6	0.41*** (0.05)	0.40*** (0.05)	0.40*** (0.05)	0.43*** (0.06)	0.42*** (0.06)	0.42*** (0.06)	0.36*** (0.06)	0.36*** (0.06)	0.35*** (0.06)	0.54*** (0.07)	0.54*** (0.07)	0.54*** (0.07)
ISCED 7-8	0.74*** (0.05)	0.72*** (0.05)	0.73*** (0.05)	0.77*** (0.06)	0.76*** (0.07)	0.76*** (0.07)	0.76*** (0.06)	0.76*** (0.06)	0.75*** (0.06)	0.85*** (0.07)	0.85*** (0.07)	0.84*** (0.07)
Household income	0.19*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.25*** (0.02)	0.25*** (0.02)	0.25*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.19*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)	0.18*** (0.02)
Neighborhood SES	0.10*** (0.02)	0.06** (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	0.07** (0.02)	0.05* (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.06** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)
School factor	0.00 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.02)	0.01 (0.01)	0.02 (0.02)	0.01 (0.03)	0.04 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.02)	0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.04* (0.02)	-0.03 (0.02)	-0.05* (0.02)
School quality (abs)		0.15*** (0.02)			0.07** (0.02)			0.07*** (0.02)		0.06** (0.02)		
School factor × school quality (abs)		-0.01 (0.01)			-0.00 (0.01)			-0.03* (0.01)		-0.01 (0.02)		
School quality (rel)			0.08*** (0.02)			0.05** (0.02)			0.05** (0.02)			0.05* (0.02)
School factor × school quality (rel)			-0.00 (0.01)			-0.01 (0.01)			-0.00 (0.01)			-0.01 (0.01)
Constant	4.45*** (0.05)	4.48*** (0.05)	4.47*** (0.05)	4.29*** (0.06)	4.30*** (0.06)	4.30*** (0.06)	4.40*** (0.05)	4.39*** (0.05)	4.40*** (0.05)	4.44*** (0.07)	4.44*** (0.07)	4.45*** (0.07)
var(school)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.03*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.01)
var(residual)	1.14*** (0.02)	1.14*** (0.02)	1.14*** (0.02)	1.30*** (0.03)	1.30*** (0.03)	1.30*** (0.03)	1.20*** (0.02)	1.20*** (0.02)	1.20*** (0.02)	0.95* (0.02)	0.95* (0.02)	0.95* (0.02)
Loglikelihood	-10671.06	-10642.28	-10660.70	-8236.98	-8232.20	-8232.96	-7876.27	-7869.06	-7872.55	-5468.67	-5463.82	-5465.20

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: All continuous predictors are z-standardized. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table S.5. Results multilevel regression models of pre-uni. track rec. [0/1] on school factor, school quality and family characteristics, by region.

	Amsterdam (N = 7,113)			Rotterdam (N = 5,278)			The Hague (N = 5,185)			Utrecht (N = 3,898)		
	(1b)	(2b)	(3b)	(1b)	(2b)	(3b)	(1b)	(2b)	(3b)	(1b)	(2b)	(3b)
Minority background (ref. = no)	0.03*	0.03*	0.03*	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	-0.06**	-0.06*	-0.06*
	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)
ISCED 0-4	-0.03	-0.03	-0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.04	-0.04	-0.04	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.03)	(0.03)	(0.03)
ISCED 5-6	0.13***	0.13***	0.13***	0.14***	0.14***	0.14***	0.10***	0.10***	0.09***	0.15***	0.15***	0.15***
	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.03)	(0.03)	(0.03)
ISCED 7-8	0.31***	0.31***	0.31***	0.32***	0.32***	0.31***	0.30***	0.29***	0.30***	0.32***	0.32***	0.32***
	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.03)	(0.03)	(0.03)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.03)	(0.03)	(0.03)
Household income	0.06***	0.06***	0.06***	0.07***	0.06***	0.06***	0.05***	0.05***	0.05***	0.05***	0.05***	0.05***
	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)
Neighborhood SES	0.03***	0.01	0.03***	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.04***	0.03***	0.04***	0.02*	0.02	0.02*
	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)
School factor	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02*	0.00	0.02*	-0.00	0.00	-0.00	-0.02*	-0.02	-0.02**
	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)
School quality (abs)		0.05***			0.02*			0.02**			0.03**	
		(0.01)			(0.01)			(0.01)			(0.01)	
School factor × school quality (abs)		-0.01*			0.01			0.00			-0.01	
		(0.01)			(0.00)			(0.01)			(0.01)	
School quality (rel)			0.02***			0.02**			0.01*			0.01
			(0.01)			(0.01)			(0.01)			(0.01)
School factor × school quality (rel)			-0.01			0.00			0.01			-0.01
			(0.01)			(0.01)			(0.00)			(0.01)
Constant	0.31***	0.31***	0.31***	0.26***	0.26***	0.26***	0.31***	0.31***	0.31***	0.28***	0.27***	0.28***
	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.03)	(0.03)	(0.03)
var(school)	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.01***	0.01***	0.01***
	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)
var(residual)	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***	0.20***
	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)	(0.00)
Loglikelihood	-4489.29	-4466.76	-4480.79	-3261.22	-3257.35	-3256.91	-3230.36	-3226.07	-3226.86	-2436.34	-2431.94	-2434.25

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: All continuous predictors are z-standardized. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table S.6. Results multilevel regression models of track recommendation on school factor, school quality and family characteristics, excluding school switchers.

	<i>DV: Track recommendation [1-6]</i>			<i>DV: Pre-university track rec. [0/1]</i>		
	(1a)	(2a)	(3a)	(1b)	(2b)	(3b)
Minority background (<i>ref. = no</i>)	0.03 (0.02)	0.05* (0.02)	0.04 (0.02)	0.01 (0.01)	0.02 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)
Parental education (<i>ref. = missing</i>)						
ISCED 0-4	-0.08* (0.03)	-0.07* (0.03)	-0.08* (0.03)	-0.02 (0.01)	-0.02 (0.01)	-0.02 (0.01)
ISCED 5-6	0.41*** (0.03)	0.41*** (0.03)	0.41*** (0.03)	0.13*** (0.01)	0.13*** (0.01)	0.13*** (0.01)
ISCED 7-8	0.76*** (0.03)	0.74*** (0.03)	0.75*** (0.03)	0.31*** (0.01)	0.30*** (0.01)	0.31*** (0.01)
Household income	0.19*** (0.01)	0.18*** (0.01)	0.18*** (0.01)	0.06*** (0.01)	0.06*** (0.01)	0.06*** (0.01)
Neighborhood SES	0.08*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.08*** (0.01)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.01* (0.01)	0.02*** (0.00)
School factor	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00)	-0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
School quality (abs)		0.11*** (0.01)			0.04*** (0.00)	
School factor × school quality (abs)		-0.00 (0.01)			0.00 (0.00)	
School quality (rel)			0.06*** (0.01)			0.02*** (0.00)
School factor × school quality (rel)			-0.01 (0.01)			0.00 (0.00)
Regional fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	4.50*** (0.03)	4.49*** (0.03)	4.50*** (0.03)	0.33*** (0.01)	0.33*** (0.01)	0.33*** (0.01)
var(school)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.01*** (0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	0.01*** (0.00)
var(residual)	1.01*** (0.01)	1.01*** (0.01)	1.01*** (0.01)	0.21*** (0.00)	0.21*** (0.00)	0.21*** (0.00)
Loglikelihood	-22359.72	-22313.07	-22341.17	-9919.06	-9885.45	-9908.41

Source: CBS microdata.

Note: $N = 15,509$. All continuous predictors are z-standardized. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.